

MEDICINE OF SAFFRON PLANT

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Saffron is a perennial herbaceous bulbous plant belonging to the Saffron family. Not found in the wild. It is planted in large areas in India, Pakistan, China, Southern Europe, Azerbaijan. The diameter of the onion is 1-2 centimeters. 5-15 leaves, pale yellow; 2 mm wide, glabrous. Flowers 1-4, yellow discharge, lower part (outer side) purple color, length 2-4 cm. Changchilari is shorter than a saffron. The calyx is long, 6-7 mm wide. It blooms in February-July, bears fruit in April-August. Because it contains essential oil, the smell is very sharp and pleasant. From 90-100 thousand saffron flowers, 1 kg of dried flower buds are obtained. Dried buds of the saffron flower are used to improve the color and taste of jam, cakes, food (to color cheese, butter, liquor, etc.), and in the perfume industry. It is used as medicine in medicine.

Saffron is the only spice whose price and value have not decreased since the Middle Ages. Information about saffron, which in the Middle Ages could be exchanged for a pack (450 g) of saffron for a thoroughbred Arabian horse.

Useful properties of saffron

In modern medicine, it is used in the preparation of eye drops and in the preparation of various general strengthening medicines. It has been proven that saffron has anticarcinogenic and antimutagenic properties. If you drink it with boiling milk, it strengthens brain function and improves memory. If consumed with honey, it helps to break down kidney stones.

Smelling the aroma of saffron relaxes a person by having a positive effect on the respiratory organs and helps to get rid of insomnia. In case of severe headache and ear cold, cotton or soft cloth soaked in saffron water and pressed on the affected part will relieve the pain. It also reduces the feeling of bloating. If saffron is used in excess, it can cause a severe strain on the senses. Saffron, added to food in excess of the norm, can lead to poisoning in addition to spoiling the food. A few grams of freshly cut quality saffron can be fatal. It is not recommended to use as a sedative for pregnant women without the advice of a specialist.

The role of saffron in folk medicine

Saffron improves digestion, stimulates the appetite, improves the vital activity of the body, people use it to strengthen the stomach, heart, liver, respiratory organs and nervous system, cleanse the kidneys, relieve pain, as a sedative,

diuretic, bile and sweat agent. are used as But it cannot be consumed during pregnancy, as it can cause premature miscarriage.

- In the treatment of oncological diseases (even at the last stage of the disease, it resists cancer tumors and stops their cell growth);
- Cleansing the blood (it renews and cleans it, therefore strengthens the cardiovascular system, nourishes all cells of the body);
- Improves brain activity (grows brain tissues, improves memory);
- Relieves neurosis;
- Relieves headache and insomnia;
- Normalizes gastrointestinal activity;
- Get rid of excess grass;
- Treats kidney and bladder (saffron mixed with honey crushes kidney and bladder stones);
- Has an antioxidant effect (improves the metabolism of energetic substances, removes harmful substances);
- Energizes the body;
- Restores eyesight, cures diseases of the retina;
- Improves erection;
- Relieves pain during the menstrual cycle;
- Treats burns and swelling of the skin;
- Relieves allergies
- Expels wind and spasms;
- Rejuvenates the whole body;
- Reduces the level of radiation in the body.

A universal recipe for eating saffron

Effect: overall strengthening and activation of the body. Cleans the blood well. Strengthens immunity. Prevents oncological diseases.

Ingredients: take 2-3 flowers of saffron and 10 raisins, put them in half a glass of cold water, leave overnight - the water will turn brown-golden. standard medicine is prepared in the morning. The duration of the treatment is 2 months. The best time to drink this medicine is spring and summer.

How to drink saffron

In order to normalize liver function and treat it, saffron is crushed like flour and eaten 20 minutes after eating. Method: lick the tip of a teaspoon with the tongue. To increase male potency, saffron, ginger medicinals and black pepper are added after cooking vegetable, meat or fish dishes.

A mixture of saffron in water is used in the treatment of heart, kidney, liver diseases, conjunctivitis, keratitis and purulent wounds. For this, one teaspoon of saffron fibers is poured into a glass of boiling water, let it rest for 20 minutes, pass through 3 layers of gauze, cool, and drink 15 grams three times a day before meals, or soak gauze in this water and apply it to the wound. cried

Saffron is the dried seeds of a subtropical plant mother belonging to the family of saffron. In folk medicine, saffron tea was drunk for patients with a weak heart and shortness of breath. Ibn Sina's opinion about saffron is as follows: "...It is astringent and a solvent. It has a twisting and adhesive feature, and it's also maturing. Its heat is moderate and unclogs: It corrects the smell and strengthens the internal organs. Drinking saffron makes the color beautiful, the eyes clear, and the heart strong. It facilitates the passage of phlegm and strengthens the respiratory organs.

Put 15-20 pinches of saffron, 1 teaspoon of high-quality blue or black tea into a half-liter teapot, and pour boiling water over it. Wrap it in a towel and let it rest for 4-5 minutes so that it gives good juice. Tea is drunk little by little.

The saffron plant is a valuable raw material for the food, pharmaceutical, and perfumery industries. Currently, saffron is grown on a total of 159.3 ha of land in the republic, including 97.3 ha in forestry and 62.0 ha in agricultural land. plantations were established.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, during his visit to Kashkadarya region on February 24-25, 2017, and in an extended meeting, according to paragraph 21 of the statement "On measures to establish saffron plantations in our republic, to meet the needs of the pharmaceutical industry, and to organize the reproduction of medicinal plants for export" LLC "Saffron Scientific Research Center" was established, and in the same year, 36.4 tons of 9-10 hummingbird saffron bulbs were imported to Uzbekistan from the Dutch company "Mts Shipper".

The cultivation of this plant and the harvesting of raw materials are considered very expensive, as it is done only by manual labor. Today, saffron is grown in more than fifteen countries, including Iran, Turkey, Azerbaijan, Russia, China, India, and Australia.

Saffron is planted in the second decade of August in the conditions of Uzbekistan, based on the scientific research carried out by the scientists of the Botany Institute of the Federal Republic of Uzbekistan and the "Saffron Scientific Research Center" LLC. For this, the selected land areas are leveled with a tractor, 60 cm wide rows are drawn, 9-10 hummingbird bulbs are planted 18-19 cm

apart, 7-15 cm deep. In this case, 1000 kg or 90 thousand pieces of sorted onions are used on 1 hectare. After planting, the onions are watered to settle in the soil. By October-November of the year of planting, saffron flowers are harvested. One of the most important and labor-intensive processes is to immediately remove the seeds from the harvested flowers on the same day, otherwise it will be difficult to separate the seeds from the dried flowers. Established saffron plantations will be weeded and loosened every spring and autumn for the coming years, and fed with local fertilizers in August.

